

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SANOUSSI****FIRST NAME: FADILA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 1%

The author used the following software: MS Word 365 on Windows 11

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Academic essay writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7-12)
2. Punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-24)
3. American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism and citations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
5. Style Guides: Chicago Manual of Style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40-56)
6. Latin abbreviations and expressions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 58-62)

WRITING AN ESSAY: METHODS AND RULES

1) INTRODUCTION

This response paper is a reaction to the ACA-401D period one on how to prepare an essay in the academic world (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024). The course pack is an interesting guide to assist students in developing a good academic writing style, ensuring consistency and adherence to academic requirements. Its latest edition, revised by Pr. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, provides primary guidance on writing essays, punctuation, avoiding plagiarism, adhering to style guidelines, and distinguishing between American and British English. The introductory tutorial video provided by Pr Cleenewerck gives an overview of citations, some differences between American and British styles, and tips on using the Word software, such as inserting footnotes.

The response paper will first outline general information on the concepts indicated above. Secondly, it will expose the reactions and elements learned throughout the course reading and the benefits drawn from it.

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2) METHODS AND RULES

a) Academic essay writing

This section outlines the main steps in drafting an academic essay: planning, researching, organising ideas, drafting, and finalising the text. It provides a methodical approach, including early topic research, drafting, and multiple revisions. Key aspects include drafting a thesis, providing evidence, and ensuring logical flow between sections (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7-12). One approach to support assertion is to “argue against yourself” by asking others how they would react to our criticism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 14). This method improves clarity and lets writers stay focused on answering the essay question thoroughly.

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Reading the essay writing section gave me a better understanding of how essential a structured approach is to produce a well-organized academic paper. The emphasis on early preparation and iterative revisions was particularly valuable, highlighting the importance of refining ideas before submitting the final draft. The guide’s insights into thesis development and argument structure encouraged me to regularly apply these methods in my writing.

b) Punctuation

This part of the course pack includes punctuation rules such as apostrophes, commas, colons, and hyphens. It emphasises clarity and conciseness in punctuation, helping students avoid typical errors and inconsistencies that can lessen the readability of their writing. Appropriate punctuation enhances readability and allows the reader to follow the text easily. The section gives various examples of what is correct and what is not (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 16-23), although presenting this in a table would have increased the readability of this section.

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Though I was familiar with most punctuation rules, this section gave me helpful explanations, especially regarding apostrophes and comma usage. The examples reinforced the need of clarity and conciseness in academic writing, and I saw how minor punctuation errors could detract from a paper’s overall professional appearance. This section made me more mindful of punctuation precision, enhancing my reader’s experience.

c) American vs. British English

A critical section discusses the distinctions between American and British English in spelling, grammar, vocabulary, and punctuation. It advises students to select one variant and apply it consistently. For example, “color” (American English) and “colour” (British English) and “organize” versus “organise” illustrate spelling differences that students are encouraged to recognise and standardise in their work. Understanding these differences is essential to avoid a mix of styles that can detract from credibility. However, differences

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are not limited to the spelling but also concern the meaning, pronunciation, ethical influences as well as punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25-32).

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Learning the distinctions between American and British English extended my understanding of how such details contribute to consistency in writing. While I have frequently used British English professionally, I now see the need to select one variation based on gathering people or institutional/customer preference. This section reminded me of the importance of tone and style consistency, which can significantly impact the clarity of my writing.

d) Plagiarism and Citations

One of the ACA-401D core messages is the importance of academic honesty. Plagiarism is defined as “using a source of information without giving credit to the author as a source of that information” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34). Adding references and sources to the authors is not only a question of ethics but also a question of credibility. However, when the evidence is obvious, references are sometimes not required. The course provides detailed guidance on avoiding plagiarism through proper citation and emphasises understanding when to credit sources. In-text citations, quotations, and paraphrases are introduced, with examples of acceptable formats to help students maintain academic integrity (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 35-37).

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That was particularly insightful in enhancing my understanding of citation practices. I found the guidance on distinguishing between quotations and paraphrasing helpful, as it clarified when and how to cite various sources. The examples helped me identify that thorough citation shows respect for original authors and strengthens my work’s credibility.

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e) Style Guides: Chicago Manual of Style

The ACA-401D course overviews the rules of style in academic writing. It discusses the role of the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) within the Euclid academic community. It shows why a consistent, recognised style is necessary for clarity and credibility in writing. Chicago Manual of Style, often known as the Turabian style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 44), covers common formatting issues such as abbreviations, capitalisation, numbers, and quotation marks. The manual provides quick references to maintain consistent formatting, particularly in footnotes, endnotes, and bibliographies.

Although I was familiar with basic citation formats, I now understand how following a specific style guide such as CMS can improve the readability and organisation of my work. Understanding the importance of a style reinforces the presentation of a paper and improves its readability. This encouraged me to be more disciplined in applying consistent formatting rules, lending greater credibility to my writing. This section also

clarified formatting nuances I might need to look into, such as capitalisation rules and the proper use of italics (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 45-47).

f) Latin abbreviations and expressions

Latin abbreviations and expressions like “i.e.” “e.g.” and “et al.” are frequently used in academic writing. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 59-61). The section describes these terms, advising students on when and how to use them correctly. This information is essential for academic papers because, when used correctly, Latin abbreviations can improve concision and clarity.

I learned a lot from the section on Latin abbreviations because I often encounter these terms but sometimes question their correct use. To maintain a formal tone in writing, the course pack provided here made clear when and how to apply these abbreviations.

3) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the ACA-401D course pack and the tutorial video offer a valuable source for understanding academic writing and the main practices in scholarly work. Each chapter addresses core aspects, from essay draft and punctuation to citation practices and style guide. These elements are essential for producing clear, credible, and ethical writing in any academic field.

The sections on essay structuring and the importance of early revisions underline how planning and clarity of purpose can strengthen an argument. Punctuation and consistency in style, as discussed in the American vs. British English and CMS guidelines sections, stress the need for uniformity, especially in international contexts where minor differences can impact readers’ perceptions. Meanwhile, the discussions on plagiarism and citations reinforced the ethical dimension of academic writing, emphasising how correct attribution respects other authors and strengthen one’s credibility.

I understand structured academic writing better, particularly citation, style consistency, and identifying differences in English versions. While I was already familiar with basic essay structures and punctuation rules, the deep dive into American vs. British English distinctions and the CMS-specific guidelines enriched my understanding of academic rules. The course could benefit anyone aiming to refine their academic writing, as it is highly organised and covers the main concepts thoroughly. It also includes nuanced topics, like using Latin abbreviations, which helped me recognise minor details contributing to an enhanced academic style. Overall, the programme has provided new approaches and enhanced my awareness of the importance of structure, precision, and ethical writing practices in producing professional-quality academic work.

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REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, dir. n.d. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo video.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *How to Write a Response Paper (RP)*. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.